

Relativistic Corrections to the 1-D Schrodinger Equation Using Fourier Series

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In previous notes, it was suggested that $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, may be written as: $\frac{1}{2m} \sum_p [p^* p f(p) \exp(ipx)]$ ((1)) and $W(x) = \sum_p [f(p) \exp(ipx)]$ ((2)). This result should hold for the relativistic case, thus one may use $p_{Rel} = p / \sqrt{1 - p^2/m^2}$ where p is the nonrelativistic momentum and $c=1$. One may then calculate expressions for ((1)) and ((2)) performing an expansion in $1/m$ to find $W = W_a + W_b$ and $\langle p_{Rel} \rangle = p + a$ correction. This may be used in both the Klein Gordon and Dirac equations, leading to an Schrodinger like equation with extra terms. One may set $W_a = W_{a0} + W_{a1}$ where W_{a0} is the Schrodinger solution, leaving a differential equation for W_{a1} . This DE depends on the relativistic equation used. Thus, one finally obtains: $W = W_{a0} + W_{a1} + W_b$ and an altered Hamiltonian. One may use both of these to calculate energy shifts using: $\langle W_{a0} + W_{a1} + W_b | H_{altered} | W_{a0} + W_{a1} + W_b \rangle - \langle W_{a0} | H | W_{a0} \rangle$. We consider the case of a Klein Gordon equation with both a scalar and vector potential, a Klein Gordon case with only a scalar potential and the Dirac equations. Given that some quantum mechanical bound particles move with speeds in the range of 10^7 m/s, it seems relativistic corrections may be important.

Fourier Series Expansion

Consider $W_{relativistic} = \int dp f(p) \exp(ipx)$, where W is the wavefunction. One may expand using:

$$p_{rel} = p / \sqrt{1 - p^2/m^2} = p + \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^3}{m^2} \quad ((3))$$

Then one has the factors:

$$\frac{d p_{rel}}{d p} = \frac{f(p) \exp(ipx)}{[1 + 3p^2/m^2] [f(p) + (d/dp f(p)) p^3/m^2] \exp(ipx) (1 + ip^3/m^2)}$$

Next:

$$\int dp \frac{d}{dp} [f p^3/m^2 \exp(ipx)] = 0 \text{ if } f \text{ dies out at high } \pm p = \text{infinity.}$$

$$= (d/dp f) p^3/m^2 \exp(ipx) + f p 3p^2/m^2 \exp(ipx) + i x f \exp(ipx) p^3/m^2$$

Thus: $W_b = 0$ and:

$$\langle p_{rel} \rangle = p + \frac{1}{2} \frac{p^3}{m^2} \int dp f \exp(ipx) \text{ where } W_b = 0 \quad ((5))$$

Here $(p+p^3/(2m^2))$ is approximated by: $p^2 + p^4/(2m^2)$

At first one may expect the Integral $\int dp f \exp(ipx)$ to be the solution of the Schrodinger equation, but this is not the case. It may be written as $\psi = \psi_0 + \psi_1$ where ψ_0 is the Schrodinger solution and ψ_1 a correction. This correction depends on the relativistic DE used.

Klein-Gordon Equation with a Scalar Potential

Consider: $(E^2 - (m+V)^2) (\psi_0 + \psi_1) = \langle \text{prel} | \text{prel} \rangle$ ((6)) $E = e + m$

Then:

$$e^2 \psi_0 - V^2 \psi_0 + 2m(e-V)\psi_1 = p^2 \psi_1 + p^4/(m^2) \psi_0 \quad ((7))$$

The last term of ((6)) is ψ_0 because ψ_1 has been dropped. One finally obtains a DE for ψ_1 which is of order $1/(m^2)$:

$$e^2 \psi_0 - V^2 \psi_0 + 2m(e-V)\psi_1 = - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \psi_1 + \frac{4}{m} \left(\frac{d}{dx} V \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} \psi_0 \right) + \frac{2}{m} \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} V \right) \psi_0 + 4(e-V)(e-V) \psi_0$$

((9))

This a Schrodinger-like equation with a complicated potential-like term. ψ_1 should be of the order of $1/(m^2)$. For a square well-potential all derivative of V terms should disappear with in the potential region.

The correction to the energy levels seems to be:

$$\begin{aligned} & \langle \psi_0 + \psi_1 | \frac{1}{2m} (p^2 + p^4/(m^2)) + V + V^2 | \psi_0 + \psi_1 \rangle - \langle \psi_0 | p^2/2m + V | \psi_0 \rangle \\ & = \langle \psi_0 | V^2 | \psi_0 \rangle + \langle \psi_0 | .5p^4/(m^2 m^2) | \psi_0 \rangle + 2 \langle \psi_1 | p^2/2m + V | \psi_0 \rangle \end{aligned} \quad ((9b))$$

The first term of ((9b)) is of the order $1/(m^2)$ while the other terms are of the order $1/(m^4)$.

Consider next, the Klein-Gordon equation with a scalar potential of $.5V$ and a vector potential of $-.5V$.

Then: $(E-.5V)^2 - (m+.5V)^2 = (e-V)(e+2m) = (e-V)2m(1+e/(2m))$ ((10))

$$2m(e-V)e \psi_0 + 2m(e-V)(1+e/2m)\psi_1 = - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \psi_1 + p^4/(m^2) \psi_0 \quad ((11))$$

In ((11)) there are order $1/m$ terms so:

$$2m(e-V)e W_{a0} + 2m(e-V)W_{a1} = -d/dx d/dx W_{a1} \quad ((12))$$

W_{a1} should be of order $1/m$. The correction to the energy levels is:

$$\begin{aligned} &\langle W_{a0} + W_{a1} | 1/2m (1-e/2m \dots) (p^*p + p^4/(m^*m) + V | W_{a0} + W_{a1} \rangle - \langle W_{a0} | p^*p/2m | W_{a0} \rangle \\ &= 2\langle W_{a1} | 1/2m p^*p + V | W_{a0} \rangle + \langle W_{a0} | 1/2m (-e/2m) p^*p | W_{a0} \rangle \quad ((13)) \end{aligned}$$

Dirac Equations

Finally, we consider the one dimensional Dirac equations combined to give:

$$(E+m+V) (-1) d/dx \{ 1/(E+m+V) d/dx u \} = (E^*E - (m+V)^2) u \quad ((14))$$

Or

$$-d/dx d/dx u + (d/dx u) (1/(E+m+V)) (d/dx V) = (E^*E - (m+V)^2) u$$

Again, one may let $u = \int dp_{rel} f(p_{rel}) \exp(i p_{rel} x)$ so the analysis seems similar to the Klein-Gordon case.

$$-d/dx d/dx u = p^*p u_b + p^4/(m^*m) (u_{a0} + u_{a1})$$

$u_b = 0$.

The RHS of ((14)) is identical to the Klein-Gordon case.

$$\begin{aligned} e^*e u_{a0} - V^*V u_{a0} + 2m(e-V)u_{a1} = -d/dx d/dx u_{a1} + p^4/(m^*m) (u_{a0} + u_{a1}) + (d/dx u) \\ (1/(E+m+V)) (d/dx V) \quad ((15)) \text{ or} \end{aligned}$$

$$e^*e u_{a0} - V^*V u_{a0} + 2m(e-V)u_{a1} = -d/dx d/dx u_{a1} + p^4/(m^*m) (u_{a0}) + (d/dx u_{a0}) (1/2m) (d/dx V)$$

Technically the $d/dx u$ on the RHS of ((15)) should go as $p+p^3/(2m^*m)$, but the second term is dropped because it is of too high an order of $1/m$.

((15)) may be solved for u_{a1} .

$V^*V u_{a0}$ and $e^*e u_{a0}$ are terms of order $1/(m^*m)$ as are other terms. Thus, u_{a1} seems to be of order $(1/m^*m)$ like in the Klein-Gordon case. Unlike the Klein-Gordon case, however, the modified Hamiltonian seems to be of the form:

$$-d/dx (1/(E+m+V)) d/dx + V \text{ so there is no } V^*V \text{ term.}$$

This is equivalent to: $(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + [d/dx V / (2m)] \frac{d}{dx} + V$

The energy levels should shift by:

$$\langle u_0 + u_1 | (-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + p^4/(m^*m) + [d/dx V / (2m)] (1-(e+V)/2m) \frac{d}{dx} + V | u_0 + u_1 \rangle - \langle u_0 | (-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + V | u_0 \rangle$$

$$\langle u_0 | [d/dx V / (2m)] \frac{d}{dx} | u_0 \rangle + \langle u_0 | p^4/(m^*m) | u_0 \rangle + 2\langle u_1 | (-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} + V | u_0 \rangle + \langle u_0 | (-(e+V)/2m) [d/dx V / (2m)] \frac{d}{dx} | u_0 \rangle \quad ((16))$$

The first two terms of ((16)) are of order $1/(m^*m)$ while the other terms are of order $1/(m^*m^*m)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we write p^n terms times a wavefunction in relativistic equations as:

$$\int dp \exp(i p x)$$

and the wavefunction itself as $W_{rel}(x) = \int dp \exp(i p x)$.

Next, we use $p = p / \sqrt{1 - p^2/(m^*m)}$ and expanded where p is the nonrelativistic momentum. This allows one to write $W_{rel}(x) = W_a(x) + W_b(x)$. $W_b=0$, but we find a correction from $\langle p^2 \rangle$. This is then inserted into a relativistic DE like the Klein-Gordon or Dirac equations and one finds that $W_a(x) = W_{a0}(x) + W_{a1}(x)$ where $W_{a0}(x)$ is the solution of the Schrodinger equation. In calculating new energy levels, modified Hamiltonians are used together with $W_a(x) = W_{a0} + W_{a1}$. It is found that corrections involving W_{a1} are of a higher order of $1/m$. The corrections of W_{a1} , however, is important in calculating the density W^*W in a nonrelativistic approximation.